

Locus of Control with Learning Achievement Student Nurse

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Abstract

Background: Locus of control is a concept that explains whether someone feels that the control of their lives is in the hands of their own hands (internal locus of control) or is in the hands of other people's hands or other things (external locus of control). Locus of control is one of the factors that influence learning achievement. **Aim:** This study aims to determine the relationship of Locus of Control with student achievement in level II of the Nurses Study Program at the Sari Mutiara Indonesia University in Medan.

Method: The research design used is descriptive correlation with cross sectional approach. The population in this study was 150 students of the Nurses Study Program at Sari Mutiara Indonesia University. The sampling technique uses a random sampling technique where the number of samples is 109 people.

Result: The results of the study with the Spearman rank statistical test obtained $p\text{-value}=0.022$ ($p<0.05$) with $r=-0.220$ ($2.0-3.99=\text{low}$).

Conclusion: The conclusion is that there is a weak relationship between Locus of Control and student achievement in level II of Nurse Study Program at Sari Mutiara Indonesia University in Medan.

Keywords: Locus of Control; Learning achievement; Student nurse

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Introduction

Nursing students are individuals who study at the college level to prepare themselves for a skill that will be used to help organize their future in the field of nursing in health services [1-9]. In the academic world, campus serves to be a sacred institution that plays the role in invention or innovation activities, conceptualization of ideas, dissemination of science and dissemination of truth pursuant to empirical data and facts [8]. According to Papalia [10], a college or university can be a means or place for an individual to develop intellectual abilities, personality, especially in practicing verbal and quantitative skills, critical thinking and moral reasoning. So student nurses are individuals who are studying at the college level. higher education, both public and private or other institutions at the same level as tertiary institutions.

Nursing students are considered to have a high level of intellect, intelligence in thinking and planning in action. Critical thinking and acting quickly and accurately are traits that tend to be inherent in every nursing student, which is a complementary principle. Characteristics of students in general, namely stability in personality which began to increase [11-14]. The main objective of nursing education is to make nursing students competent in the field of nursing. Nursing educational institutions must collaborate with clinical instructors to provide optimal learning experiences

for students [5].

The success or failure of achieving educational goals is very dependent on the learning process experienced by students both when they are at school or in their own home or family environment [15]. Learning is a process that includes three components, namely input, process and output. Input as input usually consists of students, course material, lecture facilities and facilities, lecturers, curriculum, and management applicable in the college. While the process consists of lecture strategies, instructional media, how to teach lecturers, and student learning methods. Output is the result of a learning process called achievement.

Measurement of student achievement in formal education has been determined in terms of a semester and is often referred to as midterm and final semester exams. In this case, student learning achievement within a certain period can be seen through the Grade Point Average. Learning achievement achieved by students as expected, it is necessary to pay attention to several factors that influence learning achievement, including: internal factors and external factors. In the learning process it does not always run smoothly, because in practice those who are considered successful are groups or individuals who can achieve these goals

according to the specified criteria. On the other hand, there are those who experience obstacles in achieving these goals. It is the group or individual who is thought to have learning difficulties. The predictor that is considered to have an influence in this problem is locus of control.

Initially, locus of control was viewed as a one-dimensional construct ranging on a continuum from internal to external. Internal locus of control referred to individuals' beliefs that events were contingent on their own behavior. In contrast, external locus of control referred to individuals' belief that events were not dependent on their own behavior and were instead dependent upon luck, fate, or powerful others [12,13]. Locus of control is a concept that explains whether a person feels that the control of their life is in their own hands (internal locus of control) or is in the hands of other people or other things (external locus of control) (Rotter, 1966). According to Galvin, et al [6] Locus of control is a fundamental individual difference variable that reflects individuals' beliefs about the degree of control they have over events in their lives-has been formally studied for more than 50 years. Locus of control is a term in psychology that shows a person's beliefs about what causes good things or bad things in his life, both in general and special matters such as health or academics.

This understanding of the concept was developed by Julian B. Rotter in 1954 and has since become an important aspect of personality studies [16,17]. So locus of control is the belief that every individual has regarding control over the events in his life, whether determined by factors from within himself or factors from outside himself. According to Yildiz Durak [18] Locus of control is a predictor of individual values, expectations, and characteristics. As a concept, it shows how a person perceives their own responsibility for various experiences. Individuals who see their own behavior as responsible for what happens to them have an internal locus of control, while those who view external factors and events as being most influential have an externally directed locus of control.

Locus of control is often associated with learning achievement, in this case, the behavior in carrying out learning activities which will then determine the measurable qualities of students through learning achievement. There are two types of locus of control, namely internal locus of control and external locus of control. Students with an internal locus of control can see between behavior and the results it gets as a cause and effect relationship. Students who have an internal locus of control feel confident that they have the ability and freedom to determine their behavior to control the results they receive. Students who have an external locus of control lack the ability to control their behavior because they perceive the events that occur, their successes, and failures are caused by the influence of outside forces such as luck, fate, and the control of others [9]. It is said that students with an internal locus of control will have higher learning achievement than students who have an external locus of control.

According to Smet [14] locus of control refers to the degree to which individuals perceive events in their life as a consequence of their actions, thus they can be controlled (internal control), or as something that is not related to their behavior so that they are

outside their personal control (external control). Meanwhile, [11] defines: when the achievement that is achieved by him is due to luck, fate, and is under the control of other forces, or something that cannot be predicted because of a situation around him that forces him, it is called external control.

In line with the thinking above, that locus of control has an influence on learning achievement. This thinking is proven in research conducted by Tienken & Sarraiocco [17] which proves that locus of control affects student achievement so that students with an internal locus of control feel powerful in their performance at school, and in the end, have a high level of impact on student achievement. Students who work with an external locus of control believe that their appearance is not those who control, but by lecturers or other external factors, so their performance tends to be lower. Research conducted by Hasan and Khalid [7] has proven that locus of control provides an effective contribution to student learning achievement. Students who have their internal locus of control have a higher grade point average than students who have an external locus of control, where students with their external locus of control tend to get a low achievement index.

In accordance with the above description, research on locus of control has not been conducted for nursing students, especially in Indonesia. This is what makes the researcher interested in conducting this research on nursing students, where nurse students when graduating will handle patients in the hospital with great responsibility, so the researcher ensures whether there is a relationship between locus of control and student nurse achievement.

Research Methods

This study used a descriptive correlation design using a cross-sectional approach. The population in this study was all Level II nurse students of the Sari Mutiara Indonesia University Medan 2015 Nurse Study Program with a total of 150 people. The sampling technique in this study used a random sampling technique with a sample size of 80 people. Data collection tools using a questionnaire. This locus of control questionnaire consists of 28 statements that have been tested for validity and reliability by Hasan and Khalid [7] with a Cronbach alpha value=0.72. To measure learning achievement using a questionnaire sheet filled with the GPA of each student nurse.

Results

Based on **Table 1**, it can be seen that the majority of nursing students' locus of control is internal locus of control as much as 82.6%.

Based on **Table 2**, it can be seen that the majority of the nursing

Table 1 Frequency and Percentage Distribution Based on Locus of Control Student Nurses.

Variable	n	%
Locus of Control		
Internal	90	82,6
External	19	17,4

Table 2 Distribution of Frequency and Percentage Based on Student Nursing Achievement.

Variable	n	%
Learning achievement		
Less satisfactory	20	18,3
Satisfactory	43	39,4
Very satisfy	40	36,7
With compliments	6	5,5

Table 3 Relationship of Locus of Control with Nursing Student Achievement.

Locus of Control	Learning Achievement
	$r=-0,220$ $p<0.022$

students' learning achievement was satisfactory as much as 39.4%.

Based on **Table 3**, it can be seen that p -value= 0.022 ($P<0.05$), with a value of $r=-0.220$ ($0.20-0.399$ =low), which indicates that there is a relationship between locus of control and the learning achievement of second-level students of the Nursing Study Program, with the pattern of the relationship between Locus of Control and the learning achievement obtained is low, and besides that, the direction of the relationship between the opposite variables is obtained, which means that the lower the locus of the control value, the higher the learning achievement value where the low locus of control value points to the locus of internal control.

Discussion

Locus of control student nurses

Based on the results of research conducted in class II students of the Sari Mutiara University Nurse Study Program, it was found that out of 109 respondents, the majority of 90 (82.6%) respondents had an internal locus of control.

Locus of control is a concept that explains whether a person feels that the control of their life is in their own hands (internal locus of control) or is in the hands of other people or other things (external locus of control). [13]. According to Smet [14] explains that locus of control refers to the degree to which individuals perceive events in their life as a consequence of their actions, thus they can be controlled (internal control), or as something that is not related to their behavior so that they are beyond their personal control (control external).

The results of this study were supported by Ariani [2] in a study entitled the relationship between locus of control and achievement motivation of junior high school students, it was found that 95 respondents with an internal locus of control (91.35%) and 9 people (8.65%) had an external locus of control. From the results of this study, it was found that respondents with an internal locus of control have the ability and effort and are responsible for what they do and have control over the results they will achieve while respondents with their external locus of control rely on other people in their business, do not have the ability and rely more on fate in each his efforts.

According to the researchers' assumptions, the results obtained are in line with existing statements, where the majority of respondents in this study have an internal locus of control. Based on the results of this study, most respondents believed in their abilities and believed in their own efforts. This causes the majority of respondents to have an internal locus of control, while the minority of respondents with their external locus of control do not believe in their abilities, they believe more in other people's efforts and rely on fate in their every business.

Nursing student learning achievements

Based on the results of research conducted on level II students of the Nursing Study Program Sari Mutiara Indonesia University, it was found that out of 109 respondents the majority of respondents as much as 39.4% had satisfactory learning achievement.

Learning Achievement is an assessment of the results of learning activities that are expressed in the form of symbols, numbers, letters, and sentences that can reflect the results achieved by each student in a certain period. Learning achievement cannot be separated from learning activities, because learning activities are a process, while achievement is the result of the learning process. The word learning achievement consists of two syllables, namely "achievement" and "learning". In the educational process, achievement can be interpreted as the result of the teaching and learning process, namely, mastery, emotional changes, or changes in behavior that can be measured by certain tests [1].

The results of this study were supported by Syahputra [16] in a study entitled the relationship between self-concept and student academic achievement, obtained 24 respondents (48%) with satisfactory learning achievement, 22 respondents (44%) with very satisfying learning achievement, and respondents with unsatisfactory learning achievement were 4 people (8%). According to the researchers' assumptions, that the results of the research obtained are in line with existing statements, where the majority of the respondents in this study have satisfactory learning achievement, this is evidenced by where the majority of respondents have an Achievement Index with satisfactory categories ranging from 2.75-3.0.

Relationship of locus of control with nurse student learning achievement

Based on the results of this study, it is known that from 90 people (82.6%) who have an internal locus of control, there are 12 people (11.0%) who have unsatisfactory learning achievement, 37 people (33.9%) who have satisfactory learning achievement, 36 people (33.0%) who have very satisfying learning achievement, and 5 people (4.6%) who have learning achievement with praise, while from 19 people (17.4%) who have an external locus of control, there are 8 people. (7.3%) who have unsatisfactory learning achievement, 6 people (5.5%) who have satisfactory learning achievement, 4 people (3.7%) who have very satisfying learning achievement, and 1 person (0.9%) who have learning achievement with compliments. Research results by Carden, Bryant, & Moss [4] Students were divided into two groups by a median-split of 10.5, yielding an internally oriented group of 57 and an externally oriented group of 57. The former students

showed significantly lower academic procrastination, debilitating test anxiety, and reported higher academic achievement than the latter.

From the results of this study, it was found that there are still students who still have unsatisfactory learning achievements even though they already have an internal locus of control, this could happen because the respondent has a negative self-concept. Where self-concept is one of the factors that can affect one's learning achievement. Individuals who have a positive self-concept are individuals who know very well about themselves, can understand and accept a number of very diverse facts about themselves, so that their evaluation of themselves becomes positive and can accept the existence of others. Individuals who have a positive self-concept will design goals in accordance with reality, namely goals that have a high probability of being achieved and are able to face life in front of them and think life is a process of discovery, and vice versa with individuals who have a negative self-concept.

From the statistical test results obtained P Value=0.022 ($P<0.05$), with a value of $r=-0.220$ ($0.20-0.399$ =low) which indicates there is a relationship between Locus of Control and student learning achievement with a pattern of relationship between Locus of Control. With the learning achievement obtained is low, and besides that, the direction of the relationship between the opposite variables is obtained, which means that the lower the locus of control value, the higher the learning achievement value, where the low locus of control value refers to the internal locus of control.

According to Azwar [3] that individuals who tend to have internal locus of control have characteristics, namely: like to work hard, have high initiative, always try to find solutions to problems, always try to think as effectively as possible, and always have the perception that efforts must be made if want to succeed. Meanwhile, the characteristics of individuals who tend to have an external locus of control, namely lack of initiative, have the hope that there is little correlation between effort and success, less like trying, because they believe that external factors control, and are less seeking information to solve problems.

According to Azwar [3] that individuals who have a tendency to internal locus of control prioritize their own efforts in dealing with something. They looked up to their own abilities. In addition, people with high internal locus of control tend to work hard and have the view that their efforts will be successful. Meanwhile, if the characteristics of individuals with internal locus of control are associated with the concept of motivation, it will be clear that individuals with high internal locus of control tend to have high intrinsic motivation as well.

Individuals who have external locus of control have a low morale for life. Because they consider that all the events that occur in

their lives are caused by factors of fate, luck, opportunity or even because of other people. In addition, they also tend to have low initiative and make less effort to see their own abilities. If individuals have a high external locus of control, they will assume that what happens in their life is due to external factors, such as luck, fate or caused by the actions of others. This is what is worrying if they continue to think that everything that happens in their lives is due to external factors, they will also experience despair, because they think that they have no control over their environment [3].

The results of this study are in accordance with research conducted by Hasan & Khalid [7] with the title of locus of control academic relationship with student achievement index which has proven that locus of control provides an effective contribution to student learning achievement with p value=0.02 ($p<0.05$). Students who have their internal locus of control have a higher grade point average than students who have external locus of control, where students with their external locus of control tend to get a low achievement index.

According to the researcher's assumptions about the relationship between locus of control and student learning achievement, it was found that the majority of respondents had an internal locus of control with satisfactory learning achievement. Where the results of the study show that the locus of control greatly affects the learning achievement of students. This is because students with an internal locus of control have characteristics that are able to control themselves and the environment, feel responsible for the results of their actions, have more confidence in their own abilities, and have less faith in fate. In other words, students with an internal locus of control depend on their skills, abilities, and efforts in doing their job. Based on these thoughts, there is a description that students with an internal locus of control have a strong impetus to succeed and achieve.

Conclusion

Based on the results of research on the relationship between locus of control and student learning achievement of nursing students, it can be concluded that the majority of respondents have internal locus of control, the majority of respondents have satisfactory learning achievement, and from the statistical test results obtained p value=0.022 ($P<0.05$), with a value of $r=-0,220$ ($2,0-3,99$ =low), which indicates that there is a relationship between Locus of Control and the learning achievement of second-level students of the Sari Mutiara Indonesia Nurse Study Program, with a pattern of relationship between Locus of Control and the learning achievement obtained including low, and besides that the direction of the relationship between the opposite variables is obtained, which means that the lower the locus of control value, the higher the learning achievement value.

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